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CULTURAL DETERMINANTS INFLUENCING SHIFTS IN THE PREFERRED TARGET LANGUAGE FOR STUDY IN RUSSIA

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Abstract. In the context of Russian society, the popularity of foreign languages has played a pivotal role in fostering socio-economic progress. As globalization continues to advance, proficiency in foreign languages has emerged as an indispensable asset, unlocking diverse opportunities that extend beyond mere communication to encompass facets such as international travel, professional networking, and intercultural interactions. This research article is dedicated to examining the historical and cultural determinants that shape language preferences in educational settings, scrutinizing the evolving patterns in the selection of primary target foreign languages for widespread study. Noteworthy attention is directed towards delineating the underlying factors, including economic considerations, significant shifts in the geopolitical landscape, and the establishment of new cultural affiliations in response to these dynamic influences. The article underscores the fluid nature of cultural and linguistic transformations resultant from the intricate interplay between external stimuli and internal dynamics that define societies across various developmental stages. Subsequent studies are envisaged to forecast prospective shifts in language preference trends, informed by the present analysis and the prevailing contextual factors.

Keywords: language preferences, cultural determinants, comparative study, cultural affiliations, geopolitical changes

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КУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИЧИНЫ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ ЦЕЛЕВОГО ЯЗЫКА ИЗУЧЕНИЯ В РОССИИ

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Аннотация. В России популярность иностранных языков сыграла важную роль в общественном и экономическом развитии. По мере развития глобализации владение иностранными языками приобретает решающее значение для различных возможностей, выходящих за рамки общения, - путешествий, профессиональных контактов и культурных обменов. Исследовательская работа данной статьи посвящена историческим и культурным факторам, влияющим на языковые предпочтения в образовании. Рассматриваются изменения тенденций изучения того или иного языка с течением времени. Особое внимание уделяется предпосылкам, определяющим выбор основного целевого иностранного языка для повсеместного изучения. Среди предпосылок выделяются экономические соображения, значительные изменения в геополитической картине и создание новых культурных связей, как реакция на вышеперечисленные факторы. В выводе данной статьи подчеркивается динамичный характер изменения культурных и языковых тенденций, обусловленный сложным соотношением внешних и внутренних факторов, характеризующих общество на различных этапах существования. Предполагается дальнейшее исследование с целью спрогнозировать будущие изменения тенденций выбора целевого языка на основе выполненного анализа и сопутствующих в настоящее время факторов.

Ключевые слова: языковые предпочтения, культурные детерминанты, сравнительное исследование, культурные связи, геополитические изменения

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Introduction

For an extensive duration, the discipline of "Foreign Language" has sustained its prominence as one of the most sought-after subjects in Russia. The absence of proficiency in a foreign language significantly impacts the quality of life among contemporary youth. Heightened levels of motivation, elicited by diverse stimuli, engender elevated expectations among students regarding the educational paradigms they engage with.

In the current era characterized by globalization, a proficient grasp of foreign languages exposes individuals to a myriad of prospects. These opportunities extend beyond mere communication and include avenues for seamless travel experiences, enhanced professional engagements, and meaningful intercultural exchanges. "Today's multicultural world requires a skill to be able to interact with different cultures, which seems problematic without the ability to communicate fluently in a foreign language" [10]. Possession of foreign language skills can endow students with a competitive edge in the labor market. Bilingual proficiency is often esteemed by employers as it signifies adaptability, effective communication competencies, and a broader worldview. The acquisition of a foreign language enables students to delve into diverse cultural landscapes, explore varied traditions, delve into literature, and grasp historical contexts.

The prevalent popularity of this field in Russia today is inherently entwined with historical antecedents, conjoined with the prevailing trends of globalization and the increasing interconnectedness characterizing the modern era. The confluence of these factors has elevated proficiency in foreign languages to the status of an essential aptitude requisite for successful communication and collaboration. Students are afforded various prospects including the chance to partake in international travel, pursue educational pursuits in foreign countries, explore potential job opportunities abroad, engage in immersive cultural experiences, and participate in the vibrant exchange of cultural richness. Delving into the study of foreign languages not only serves to bolster cognitive capacities but also acts as a catalyst for expanding career horizons and cultivating a deeper understanding of diverse cultures, thereby fostering a heightened sense of cultural awareness.

The aim of this research paper is to investigate the cultural factors influencing the transition of the target language of education in Russia. The selection of languages for educational purposes is multifaceted, with considerations spanning from the language's popularity to its wide utilization in global business transactions, academic research, scientific endeavors, and tourism. Additionally, the significance attached to learning a specific language may correlate with the historical and political relationships prevalent between nations.

The consideration of economic factors plays a significant role in determining the language chosen for educational pursuits. Recent developments in global politics have highlighted China's growing importance as a key economic partner, leading to an increased interest in learning Chinese as a primary or secondary language among students on a global scale. Additionally, the geographical location of a nation also plays a pivotal role in shaping preferences for specific target languages. The choice of languages for study in the contemporary world is influenced by a mix of economic demands, geopolitical shifts, and geographical considerations, showcasing the complex interplay of factors guiding language selection. This convergence of forces underscores the evolving and interconnected landscape of language learning in today's global context.

It is paramount to underscore the substantial financial investment required for foreign language acquisition, encompassing expenses such as instructional materials, faculty, and requisite equipment. Hence, each nation delineates its preferred target language(s), with certain countries opting for a diverse array of languages for study. Presently, English stands as the obligatory foreign language of study in Russia. Concurrently, within select high schools emphasizing linguistics and linguistic faculties, students engage with languages such as French, German, Spanish, Chinese, and Arabic.

Across Europe, English also holds sway as the primary foreign language; however, a noteworthy proportion of students, approximately 60%, pursue the study of two or more foreign languages as part of their educational curriculum. The selection of specific languages is influenced by factors like geographical proximity and linguistic similarities. For instance, in Italy

and Portugal, a preference for French is observed, whereas German garners popularity among students in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Poland, and Denmark. Furthermore, Spain finds favor in Sweden and France.

The study of Russian as a foreign language has garnered acclaim in Europe as well. Notably, a substantial segment of students in Baltic countries such as Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia, and Bulgaria opt for Russian as a foreign language of study.

Methodology

The research paper draws upon the scholarly contributions of Russian academics, focusing on the role of cultural motivations in shaping the shift in the preferred language of education within Russia. Exploring the multifaceted issues surrounding the preparation of foreign language educators for effective instructional delivery, the study delves into the intricate dynamics at play. Utilizing a blend of historical examination and comparative analysis, the authors meticulously dissect the intricate interplay of cultural elements that potentially influence the evolution of language preferences in the educational landscape of the nation. By scrutinizing the historical roots and conducting cross-cultural investigations, the study aims to unravel the nuanced relationship between cultural forces and the language policies implemented in educational settings, offering valuable insights into this complex phenomenon.

Through the lens of historical analysis, the researchers meticulously traced the trajectory of language policies, educational reforms, cultural paradigms, and societal transformations that have gradually shaped the selection of the target language in the Russian educational landscape [7]. Delving into a rich tapestry of historical documents, governmental reports, and educational literature, the scholars identified pivotal cultural determinants that underpin the evolution of language preferences.

Employing a comparative approach, this study juxtaposed linguistic trends, political dynamics, and cultural influences in Russia with analogous patterns observed in diverse global contexts. By leveraging comparative methodologies, the researchers gleaned insights into the ways in which cultural factors wield sway over language selection and educational outcomes, shedding light on the intricate interplay between culture and language acquisition.

By synergizing these diverse research techniques, the authors conducted a thorough exploration of the cultural catalysts precipitating shifts in the target language of instruction in Russia. This comprehensive approach not only illuminated the dynamics of preferences and pedagogical practices within the realm of language education but also furnished valuable insights into the intricate interplay of cultural diversity within the educational sphere.

Discussion

Over an extended period, languages such as German, French, Spanish, and Italian enjoyed popularity within Russia; however, they underwent a gradual wane in prominence, eventually giving way to the enduring dominance of English.

The erstwhile favoritism towards the French language, particularly evident during the 1980s, can be attributed to a confluence of historical and cultural factors. Noteworthy is the esteemed status accorded to French as the language of diplomacy, culture, and education during that era, rendering it a prestigious subject of study. The establishment of robust cultural affinities between Russia and France further catalyzed the uptake of the French language among learners [8]. Moreover, the entry of a significant foreign entity onto the Russian banking landscape, exemplified by the presence of Societe Generale, exerted a discernible influence on the nation's financial milieu. Notably, Societe Generale Vostok, a universal bank (presently Rosbank), inaugurated its inaugural representative office in the USSR in 1973.

Towards the close of the twentieth century, Russia embarked on a strategic innovation initiative aimed at enhancing the economic and social fabric through the implementation of a comprehensive array of measures targeting innovation and research processes. Within this landscape of progressive reforms, the automotive manufacturing sector emerged as a focal point. Established in 1899, the French automobile giant Renault entered the Russian market by inaugurating its maiden representative office in Moscow in 1992. Subsequently, in 1998, a pivotal agreement between France and Russia gave birth to the Autoframos joint venture. By the conclusion of 2006, Renault had ascended to the pinnacle as the best-selling car brand in Russia, underscoring the transformative impact of

global economic integration and the nation's burgeoning engagement with the international community [11]. The increasing significance of linguistic competence within cross-cultural collaborations saw a rise in the demand for proficiency in French.

However, the post-Soviet era witnessed a shift away from French towards English due to its dominance in international business and communication. Presently, French continues to hold a place in the educational curriculum of schools and institutes of higher learning, albeit under the designation of a "Second Foreign Language." There has been a significant drop in student enrollment for French courses in recent years, as English has increasingly become the favored foreign language for study over this period.

Nevertheless, pockets of exceptional dedication to the French language persist in select educational institutions, exemplified by establishments like the Alexandre Dumas French Lyceum in Moscow and the Andre Malraux French School in Saint Petersburg. These institutions serve as bastions of cultural richness and historical significance, endeavoring to uphold the legacy of French language and heritage. Amidst concerted efforts to promote the study of French in Russia, the endeavor faces stiff competition within the contemporary educational landscape from a plethora of alternative linguistic offerings, highlighting the evolving linguistic preferences of students and the dynamic nature of language acquisition trends.

Throughout the Soviet era, the ascent of German as a favored language in Russia mirrored a burgeoning trend. The historical and cultural affinities between Russia and Germany emerged as a primary catalyst for this linguistic surge. German's standing as the language of science, literature, and technology further fueled interest among Russian residents, as proficiency in German presented a gateway to a wealth of academic and cultural resources emanating from Germany.

The global prominence of Germany played a pivotal role in reshaping trade dynamics at an international level. The reunification of Germany and the dissolution of the USSR heralded a transformative period, fostering qualitative shifts in trade relations between nations. German corporations swiftly entered the burgeoning Russian market, navigating the transition towards a quasi-market economy, capitalizing on the

vast consumer base of approximately 140 million people eager for novel and high-quality goods. Notable among the influx of German entities venturing into the Russian market were industry giants such as Volkswagen, Mercedes, Siemens, Metro AG, Bosch, and Adidas. These companies not only established a formidable presence but also expanded their operations over time, thereby kindling interest in the study of the German language among the populace.

However, the zenith of German's popularity in Russia underwent a gradual decline, influenced by a confluence of factors. Shifting geopolitical landscapes, economic transformations, and the pervasive influence of the English language collectively contributed to this descending trajectory. Concurrently, educational reforms and realignments in curriculum priorities within Russian educational institutions played a pivotal role in diminishing the emphasis placed on learning German.

During the 1990s, Spanish was incorporated into the curriculum of schools across several regions in Russia. The widespread adoption of the Spanish language stemmed from its global prevalence, with approximately 300 million individuals worldwide conversing in Spanish during that period. The burgeoning utilization of Spanish within Russia was emblematic of the positive economic and political transformations unfolding in Spain and Spanish-speaking nations, bolstering the multifaceted relations between Russia and Spain encompassing realms such as economy, education, and culture. This underscored the pivotal role played by the Spanish language in fostering international cooperation during that era, stimulating a burgeoning interest in the diverse cultures and peoples of Spanish-speaking countries as well as serving as a motivational force for its study.

The academic pursuit of Spanish not only exposed students to the linguistic and cultural tapestry of various peoples but also illuminated the rich contributions that Spanish-speaking cultures had made to both European and global cultural heritage. Students were afforded the opportunity to engage with distinct forms of governance, social norms, and the authentic cultural legacies of Spanish-speaking communities [3]. The incorporation of Spanish as an academic discipline necessitated the development of a comprehensive curriculum, serving as a cornerstone in guiding students' communicative and cognitive endeavors.

The increasing prominence of Spanish-speaking nations on the global stage, alongside the rich cultural legacies of Spanish-speaking regions, has positioned the Spanish language as an appealing choice for many Russian learners. Nonetheless, shifts in geopolitical landscapes and economic imperatives could have played a role in diminishing the allure of Spanish language studies within Russia. As global dynamics and priorities evolve, the demand for Spanish proficiency among Russian learners may have waned, resulting in a decline in the enrollment of students pursuing Spanish language education at educational institutions.

It is noteworthy to acknowledge that the cultural rationale behind alterations in the preferred language of instruction in Russia is intricate and reflective of the dynamic nature of global linguistic trends.

During this period, the subject matter was examined by distinguished scholars and educators such as N. A. Erofeev in "Foggy Albion: England and Englishmen through the eyes of Russians" (1982), A. L. Mikhashchenko in "Educational school and pedagogical thought of the Southern Trans-Urals" (1995), V. V. Safonova in "Cultural and linguistic expansion and its manifestations in language policy in education" (2002), I. M. Sinagatullin in "New Millennium: the role and place of a foreign language in the world multicultural society" (2002), M. V. Bulygina in "Foreign language as an academic subject in historical and pedagogical research at the regional level" (2007), and A. I. Bogdanova in "Using the cultural component of the content of the discipline 'Foreign language' in the process of forming tolerance" (2015).

Primarily, it is essential to establish the concept of "target language". Numerous scholars in the realm of foreign language pedagogy, notably including David Little (1995) and Hazel Crichton (2009), propose that the term "target language" refers to a second language acquired within a scholastic or university setting. Interaction in the target language is advocated to facilitate fundamental communication skills among learners. Utilizing the target language as the principal mode of communication can act as an impetus for students, fostering successful comprehension and expression in a foreign language context.

Therefore, the language chosen as the medium of instruction signifies the particular language that students aim to excel in by utilizing various methods like traditional academic programs, language classes, independent learning, or unconventional educational approaches. This targeted language acquisition approach underscores the diverse paths students can take to achieve proficiency in the language of their choice.

In our research on "Cultural rationales underpinning the transition of the target language of education in Russia," the target language of instruction refers to the foreign language(s) selected by Russian students for academic or personal linguistic goals. These languages, such as English, German, French, Chinese, or Spanish, are chosen for cultural enrichment, economic opportunities, academic pursuits, or individual motivations.

English has gained extensive usage in the realms of international commerce, scientific advancements, technological innovations, and entertainment realms, rendering it indispensable for cross-border communication and cooperative ventures on a worldwide scale. With Russia progressively integrating into the global economic landscape and engaging with the international community, the imperative for English language proficiency has risen markedly.

Over time, a discernible trend emerges where the upper echelons of society exhibit heightened curiosity towards English literature, marked by the emergence of translations of literary works penned by English authors. English fiction, with its portrayal of British daily life, psychological nuances, and moral ethos, garnered particular attention. Notably, N. A. Yerofeyev, a Soviet historian renowned for his expertise in modern British history, noted a surge in the influx of printed materials originating from Great Britain into Russia during this era [5].

Notably, figures such as the Russian ambassador Prince H. A. Lieven (1812-1834) held prominent positions in England. Successive to Lieven, L. Matusevich (1834) embarked on diplomatic endeavors aimed at enhancing Russo-British relations, followed by A. K. Meyendorff (1838), a governmental official within the manufacturing sector.

Russia's burgeoning interest in novel English technologies and scientific advancements prompted the influx of another substantial contingent of Russian expatriates to England: scientists and technicians. Among this cohort were esteemed professionals such as engineers specializing in diverse fields including railway construction, exemplified by P. P. Melnikov. Moreover, medical scientists like R. Niber, astronomers such as I. Simonov, and specialists in agricultural sciences like S. Maslov and Ya. Linovsky, also found themselves among the ranks of Russian intellectuals seeking knowledge and collaboration within the English scientific milieu [5].

Upon scrutinizing periodicals, it becomes apparent that the War of 1812 played a discernible role in fostering the dissemination and prestige of the English language in Russia. This phenomenon led to the amplification and consolidation of trade and cultural bonds between Russia and England. Concurrently, a period marked by profound cultural and educational reforms unfolded, engendering an upsurge in the significance accorded to international trade and diplomatic relations [6]. The evolving geopolitical landscape, coupled with the escalating prominence of global interactions, notably underscored the mounting necessity of foreign language proficiency, particularly in English. Mastery of the English language emerged as a vital asset indispensable for facilitating seamless trade, diplomatic discourse, and cultural interchange not solely with Western European counterparts but also extended to engagements with the United States of America.

Translations of English fiction into Russian increased as English magazines became more prevalent, demonstrating a growing Russian interest in English daily life, politics, and economics. This shift in reading preferences indicated a curiosity among Russians about various aspects of English culture and society. In alignment with this trend, N. A. Yerofeyev observed that "the press of that time was very active in creating the image of England and the British. In contrast to literature, where the reader, as a rule, found thoughts thought out and put in a certain connection, newspapers and magazines were limited to the supply of raw material, so to speak, although parried in a certain spirit" [5].

According to the research conducted by N. E. Chernyavskaya, N. V. Kireeva, and E. N. Koreneva on the historical proliferation of the English language in Russia, they assert that the increasing popularity of English can be attributed to a confluence of external political and cultural factors within Russian society. This demand for understanding extended beyond merely mastering the language to encompass a comprehensive grasp of English culture. While acknowledging that English was not as prevalently spoken as German or French within Russian societal circles, the exposure to English cultural achievements was notably substantial through literary works and advancements in scientific collaborations [4].

Scholars indicate that the significant rise of the English language began in the early 19th century, driven by increased English language resources, educational exchanges, and visits to England. This period marked a notable influence of English across various societal levels in Russia, integrating it into public, private, and home education, with attending English high schools becoming prestigious among the elite, showcasing the high regard for English education. "After visiting Britain and becoming acquainted with its culture, scientists, translators, teachers, and authors of English language textbooks emerged as key conduits of English culture and promoters of the language in Russia. Not only did they hold admiration for Britain, but they also endeavored to impart English culture, literature, and language to Russian society" [4].

Moving towards the 1950s, notable scientific works and publications started emerging. The introduction of a new foreign language, particularly English, into the school system faced a challenge: the scarcity of English-speaking teachers. Consequently, the state initiated the establishment of a specialized field, "English teacher," in pedagogical universities, from where young professionals were deployed across the USSR post-graduation. While it took some time for the development of high-quality textbooks and effective teaching methods, by the era of Perestroika, the vast majority of Soviet students were studying English as a foreign language.

In the 1960s, spurred by the political climate, a vigorous campaign promoting English language learning was launched. This period witnessed the inaugu-

ration of specialized schools, enhancements in secondary education curricula, and the integration of English as a distinct subject in universities.

By the closing of the twentieth century, English had gained substantial popularity in Russia owing to external political, economic, and cultural forces that necessitated societal familiarity not only with the language but also with the culture. Exposure to English cultural accomplishments in Russia was facilitated through intensive literary dissemination and robust scientific exchanges.

Numerous factors played a pivotal role in fostering a deep engagement with English culture in Russia during this era. Foremost among these factors were political considerations. The end of the Cold War and the improvement of relations between Russia and Western countries, especially English-speaking nations, created opportunities for increased cultural exchange [11]. The shift towards political openness and enhanced global collaboration facilitated the assimilation of English cultural elements into Russian societal fabric.

According to M. V. Rybak, the closure of the twentieth century witnessed substantial transformations across political, economic, and social domains that fundamentally reshaped the landscape of public affairs. The author contends that the educational system underwent significant overhauls during this period. The fall of the Iron Curtain and the rise of globalization ignited a surge in Russian interest in foreign languages. This curiosity stemmed from growing connections with the Western world and international intrigue in Russia's evolving landscape. As a result, acquiring foreign language skills became essential for effective cross-border communication [9].

The surge of economic globalization and the deepening interlinkages within markets have underscored the imperative of English proficiency for commercial and trade undertakings. During the 1990s, Russia's accession to prominent international bodies such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Trade Organization (WTO) facilitated its integration into the global economic framework. English has ascended to the forefront as the primary medium of communication in international business, finance, and trade transactions.

M. V. Rybak posits that amidst the backdrop of burgeoning international collaboration in the 1990s, the educational community directed its focus towards the reinforcement of foreign language instruction, with particular emphasis on English. Through meticulous exploration, the author delves into the examination of how socio-cultural and pedagogical influences have shaped the evolution of foreign language teaching methodologies. The era witnessed a pronounced intensification of cross-cultural engagements between Russia and Western nations following the dissolution of the USSR. The evolution of international interactions necessitated individuals proficient in a foreign language to facilitate seamless communication [9].

In her scholarly investigation, M. V. Bulygina delves into the inquiry concerning the establishment of specific academic disciplines, notably foreign languages. She contends that as the twenty-first century unfolds, there is a burgeoning need for historical and pedagogical exploration, particularly in elucidating the genesis of language-focused subjects spanning from ancient languages to contemporary foreign languages. It is imperative to discern the intrinsic characteristics and socio-historical aspects that have shaped the inception and advancement of a foreign language as an educational domain.

M. V. Bulygina underscores the existence of established historical and pedagogical methodologies for conducting such inquiries in the contemporary context. These include civilizational, concrete-historical, system-historical, class-based, cultural, axiological, paradigmatic, and anthropological approaches [2].

During the early years of the 21st century, there has been a focus on studies concerning the pedagogy of teaching the subject of "Foreign Language (English)" and the cultivation of student tolerance. This era presents the educational sector with the intricate challenge of equipping the youth for life within a diverse and multicultural milieu. In her scholarly exploration, A. I. Bogdanova addresses the vital aspect of fostering constructive intercultural engagement founded on principles of tolerance.

The discipline of "Foreign Language" serves as a platform to instill tolerance among students, with its curriculum embodying a multicultural essence. Multicultural education not only encompasses the cultural

background of the learner acquiring a foreign language but also encompasses the cultural heritage of the country whose language is being studied. This duality engenders an internal discourse for students as they engage in the learning process [1].

Conclusions

The exploration of language policy, educational reforms, cultural influences, and societal shifts in Russia reveals a complex interplay of historical factors that have shaped the choice of the target language in educational settings. By delving into historical documents and scholarly literature, researchers have identified key cultural determinants that underlie language changes in the Russian context.

By examining the interplay of cultural elements on language choices and educational achievements, comparative studies have illuminated connections between linguistic patterns, political landscapes, and cultural impacts not only in Russia but also across various global contexts. This

comparative approach deepens our understanding of the intricate relationship between cultural diversity and language education practices.

Moreover, the interactions between individuals who have experienced British culture and those who share it have positioned them as essential conduits of English culture and language dissemination in Russia. Their efforts not only contribute to the admiration for British culture but also play a significant role in transmitting English culture, literature, and language to Russian society.

In light of these findings, it becomes evident that the influence of these intricate processes on the authentic culture of the Russian Federation permeates various facets of societal life. This pervasive influence underscores the importance of conducting further analysis to delve deeper into the nuanced ways in which these cultural dynamics intersect with and shape the broader spectrum of Russian cultural identity across different domains within society.

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